

AN EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL STUDY OF PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES WITH CUTOUTS

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ABSTRACT

A series of experiments was performed to study the progressive failure of T800/3900-2 Graphite/Toughened Epoxy laminates with various lay-ups and cutouts under uniaxial tensile load. Three lay-ups and five specimen geometries, including nonsymmetric specimen geometries such as the side slit and the angle slit, were tested. A material damage accumulation model was implemented into the finite element code ABAQUS and used to predict the failure response of the laminates. This model includes three in-plane failure modes: matrix cracking, fiber/matrix shear out and fiber tensile breakage. The model predicts failure mode, extent of damage and stiffness degradation due to failure, and ultimate failure of the material. Experimental results and model predictions are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites have become an important class of engineering materials. Laminated composites, for example, find wide applications as structural members. It is necessary to characterize the response of composite components under all anticipated loadings. Since holes and slits exist in many structural components, composite laminates with cutouts are a problem of great practical interest. The stress concentration near the cutout frequently causes structural failure. Stress concentrations in composite laminates have been studied extensively for more than two decades [1]. Models are available for predicting the strength of laminates with and without cutout. Most of these models are semi-empirical. They require experimentally determined parameters that are sensitive to laminate geometry and lay-up. This approach for predicting strength is experimentally expensive since a new set of parameters is needed whenever there is a change in the laminate geometry or lay-up.

Another approach for predicting strength in composite laminates is using progressive failure analyses. One popular method using this approach is to simulate a structural problem with the finite element method and predict laminate failures with a material damage model. To be practical, the material model should only use material properties of the lamina (ply) that are independent of laminate geometry and lay-up. Effects of laminate geometry and lay-up should be accounted for by the finite element calculation. This approach is more computationally expensive, but is much more efficient experimentally. The progressive failure analysis approach has attracted much attention because of its non-empirical nature. An example of a material damage model suitable for this approach was recently proposed by Shahid and Chang [2]. This model was shown to match limited experimental data for some cutout geometries such as a center circular hole and a center slit.

This paper presents a combined experimental and computational study of progressive failure in composite laminates with various lay-ups and cutouts under in-plane tensile load. The long term

Table 1. Test summary

Panel ID	Lay-up %	Geometry	X-ray radiography
70	25/50/25 16 plies	A	pre-test
		B	
		C	
		D	pre-test, 80% and 90% of failure load
		E	
54V	10/40/50 20 plies	B	pre-test
		D	pre-test & 90% of failure load
		E	
76	17/67/17 24 plies	B	pre-test
		D	pre-test & 90% of failure load
		E	

goal of this investigation is to develop a constitutive model for fiber reinforced composites that is suitable for predicting progressive failure of general laminates under general loads.

EXPERIMENTS

A series of experiments was performed to study the progressive failure of T800/3900-2 Graphite/Toughened Epoxy laminates. As shown in Table 1, three lay-ups and five geometries were included. The distribution of ply orientation is indicated as 'x/y/z' in the second column of the table, where x, y and z are percentages of 0, ±45 and 90 degree plies, respectively. The ply angle is measured counterclockwise from the loading axis that is vertical. Panel 70, [(45/90/-45/0)₂]_s, is quasi-isotropic. Panel 54V, [-45/0/45/90₂/-45/90₂/45/0]_s is dominated by 90 degree ply. Panel 76, [45/90/-45/0/-45/45/90/45/-45/0/45/-45]_s, is dominated by ±45 degree ply. All three panels have different thickness. The nominal thickness of a ply is 0.188 mm.

Specimen geometries are shown in Figure 1. Geometry A has a uniform gage area. The cutouts in geometry B, C, D and E specimens are circular hole, slit, slant slit, and side slit, respectively. Since we did not repeat the characterization of T800/3900-2 unidirectional laminate, geometries A, B and C specimens were used to verify the model parameters. The cutouts in D and E are not

Figure 1 Sample geometry and setup

symmetric with respect to specimen axes. The angle between the loading axis and the slant slit is 60 degrees, which is not aligned with any fiber direction.

After machining, all samples were examined by using X-ray penetrant-enhanced radiography to ensure they were free of defect. Most samples were loaded monotonically to failure. Some samples were first loaded to 80 or 90 percent of the failure load, then they were unloaded and removed from the loading frame for making X-ray radiographs. These samples were loaded again to failure. Fractured surfaces were examined visually immediately after each test.

It is known that T800/3900-2 laminates behave consistently, and its scatter in experimental data is smaller than many other polymeric composites. Therefore, only three replicas were used in each test condition. Tests were performed on an Instron screw driven system. The extension rate was about 5×10^{-3} mm/s. One biaxial extensometer and one clip-on gage were used to monitor the deformation during loading. The biaxial extensometer has three channels: two independent channels (A and B) for axial strain and one (T) for transverse strain. Gages A and B have the same gage length of 25.4 mm; the gage length of T is adjustable. The clip-on gage (C) was modified to have a long gage length of 96.5 mm. A typical setup of type E specimen is shown in figure 1.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Verifying the damage accumulation model requires experimental results not only on laminate strength but also on deformation, damage and failure. Only few experiments provide such complete information. The experiments provide data for bench-marking in-plane models and guiding future model development.

DEFORMATION

Load-displacement curves of D and E samples are plotted in Figure 2. The ordinate, far field stress, is the load divided by the original area of the uniform cross-section that does not have a cutout. The abscissa is the measured displacement normalized by its gage length. Most of the plots show only the results of a typical specimen. The plot of 76E has the results of all three specimens on it to demonstrate the small experimental scatter of these laminates.

During a test, there was occasionally click noise from the sample. When the loading was greater than 80 percent of the failure load, one or two loud pop sounds could be heard; then finally came the catastrophic failure. Some curves in Figure 2 are not continuous; they shift to the right at some places. The horizontal shift indicates a sudden increase in displacement. It relates to the popping sound during the test. The cause of this shift could be the real deformation of the sample, a slip (or jump) of the gage caused by a stress wave, or a combination of the two. In some tests the clip-on gage was glued on the specimen so gage slip (or jump) could be eliminated; however, the sudden increase in deformation still existed but had a smaller magnitude. Thus, the sudden increase in displacements measured by extensometer might include both components: sample deformation and gage slip.

DAMAGE

Figure 3 shows the radiographs of D and E specimens, which illustrate the damage around the slits. In all cases matrix crackings in 0, 90 and ± 45 degree plies are all noticeable in the damaged area. Major matrix crackings in 0 and ± 45 degree plies are found tangent to the slit boundary. Matrix crackings in 90 degree plies are more evenly distributed without a dominant one. By comparing the damage of 70D specimens at 80 and 90 percent of the failure load, it is clear that at higher load the damaged area is larger and the crack density is higher. Although crack patterns look somewhat similar, they vary among geometries and lay-ups. For example, in specimen 54D3, the 90 degree matrix crackings extend from the end of a slit to the edge of the sample; in specimen 76E6, matrix crackings are clustered along two major cracks in ± 45 degree plies.

Figure 2 Load -displacement curves of D and E specimens

FAILURE

Typical failed D and E samples are illustrated in Figure 4. The 54D samples have fracture planes normal to the loading direction. The side view of these specimens (not shown here) revealed that all plies were broken at the same location except one surface 45 (or -45) degree ply that was debonded from the rest of the laminate. This suggested that 90 degree plies failed by matrix cracking, but 0 and ± 45 degree plies failed by fiber breakage.

Figure 3 Radiographs of D and E specimens

For 76D samples, there is no unique fracture plane. Cracks were all initiated at slit ends, but they propagated in different directions depending on the ply direction. Most of the broken edges of ± 45 degree plies are ± 45 degree from the direction of loading; that is, the fracture is parallel to the fiber direction. Therefore, the failure of ± 45 degree plies is mostly matrix cracking. A large fractured zigzag area can be seen from the side of the specimen. The failure mode of 70D samples falls in between 54D and 76D cases.

Broken samples of 54E and 70E show their failure modes are similar to 54D; there is a common fracture plane with the exception of the surface plies. The failure surface of 76E samples is comparable to 70D; both fiber breakage and matrix cracking are observed in the ± 45 degree plies.

Figure 4 Failed specimens

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

In the computational study, we used the commercial finite element code ABAQUS [3] and a user defined material damage model to predict the notch strength of the tested laminates. Results generated from the above experiments were used to assess the accuracy of this modeling method.

The damage model implemented into ABAQUS was based on a progressive failure model recently proposed by Shahid and Chang [2]. The model predicted the type of failure, the extent of damage, and the degradation in material properties as the loading progressed and failure occurred. Only three in-plane failure modes were considered: matrix cracking, fiber matrix shear-out, and fiber tensile breakage. Failure and damage were tracked at the element level for each layer. A crack density state variable (number of cracks per inch) measured the extent of damage in the matrix. A cumulative fiber failure area state variable measured the extent of damage in the fibers. More details on the theory of the implemented damage model can be found in reference 2. Shahid and Chang implemented their model in a special purpose code called PDCOMP [2]. In this study, the material damage model was implemented into ABAQUS through provided user interface subroutines UMAT and VUMAT [3]. For computational efficiency, the part for calculating the material degradation due to matrix cracking was not implemented into UMAT and VUMAT. PDCOMP was used to generate these results, which was then used by ABAQUS. Thus, the degradation was not calculated at every material point, and at every increment in the ABAQUS analysis. We believe the error caused by this simplification was small.

A total of fifteen material parameters including moduli, strengths, and statistical parameters for material degradation rules were required for the composite damage model. The same fifteen parameters were used in all analyses, for all laminate configurations. Table 2 shows the values of these parameters for the T800/3900-2 Graphite/Toughened Epoxy composites [4]. These parameters were obtained independent from the above experiments. The standard version of ABAQUS was used to analyze the quasi-static uniaxial tensile load. However, in a few analyses, we encountered numerical convergence problems due to large distortions of elements that had fiber failures. For these analyses, we used the ABAQUS explicit version with mass scaling to by-pass the convergence problem. The uniaxial tensile load of a displacement controlled test was simulated by fixing the bottom edge of the laminates and displacing the top edge upward. Figures 6 and 7 show finite element results for case 76E. These were typical results obtained from the finite element analyses. Figure 6 shows a comparison of the load versus displacement data, the undeformed and the deformed mesh. Figure 7 shows the crack density just before ultimate laminate failure occurred for the first four layers, the 45, 90, -45 and 0 degree plies respectively. These figures can be compared with the 76E6, 90% x-ray radiograph shown in figure 3. Note that in the x-ray photograph, the dye penetrant was only applied in the notch vicinity. Thus any failure far away from the notch can not be seen in the photograph. Both measured and predicted results show very high crack density right around the notch tip. The analysis predicted fiber failure only at the notch tip.

Figure 6 Load-displacement curve, deformed and undeformed meshes

Figure 7 Predicted crack density

Table 2 Material properties and constants used in the calculations

E_{xx}	E_{yy}	G_{xy}	G_{yz}	ν_{xy}	α	X_t	α_{xx}	α_{yy}	T_{cure}	G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}	η	δ	β
MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa			MPa	1/C	1/C	C	kJ/m ²	kJ/m ²			
152	9.3	6.2	3.7	0.3	8E-15	2.8	4E-07	3E-07	177	0.15	0.28	8	0.055	8

Table 3 summarizes notch strength comparisons between experimental and computational results for all cases. The values of experimentally measured strength are averages of three tests. The average error was 6.8 percent. The standard deviation of the error was 4.7 percent. All predicted strengths were within 15 percent of measured strengths. This result shows that the implemented damage model can predict the notch strength of laminates with different geometry and different lay-up relatively well. Note that no empirical data, such as characteristic length, was used in the analyses to account for the different notch geometries and different lay-ups.

Table 3 Notch strength comparison

Specimen	Measured strength (MPa)	Predicted strength (MPa)	Error (%)
70A	915	979	+ 6.9
70B	396	402	+ 1.5
54B	217	207	- 4.6
76B	291	335	+ 15.2
70C	385	327	- 15.1
70D	386	378	- 2.1
54D	257	280	+ 8.8
76D	317	336	+ 5.9
70E	219	210	- 4.2
54E	145	149	+ 2.8
76E	223	241	+ 8.1

CONCLUSIONS

Experiments to determine the strength and failure mode of symmetric and nonsymmetric cutouts under in-plane tensile loading were performed. A damage accumulation model was implemented into ABAQUS to simulate the experiments. Model predictions of laminate deformation, damage and strength compare favorably with experimental results.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the U.S. Department of Energy under Contract DE-AC04-94AL85000. The authors wish to thank Ms. Hui Bau at Boeing 777 Empennage Group for providing composite panels and technical discussions. The assistance of Michael Tracy and Yanmin Yan in the experimental work is gratefully acknowledged.

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